

Rewards and Job Performance of Teachers in Private Secondary Schools in Rukungiri District

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Abstract:- This study was to establish the relationship between rewards and job performance of teachers in private secondary schools of Rukungiri district. This was assessed through investigating whether there is a relationship between financial rewards and job performance and non-financial rewards and job performance in private secondary schools of Rukungiri district. The study employed a cross-sectional survey design. The study targeted teachers in the five chosen private secondary schools in Rukungiri District 100 teachers and key informants (head teachers and school bursars) of the selected schools together making a total of 110 individuals. The sample size of 86 respondents was determined based on Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table. The researcher sampled stratified random sampling in the selection of the 5 schools and purposive sampling on the head teachers and bursars. Results revealed that there is a strong positive correlation between financial rewards and job performance of teachers as this was evidenced by the correlation coefficient of 0.784 that is statistically significant since p -value $0.032 < 0.05$. The results in the table 5 above showed a moderate positive relationship between non-financial rewards and job performance of teachers ($r=0.526$). Based on the study findings, the researcher concludes that financial rewards and non-financial rewards were poor and these were related to the current poor job performance of teachers in private secondary schools in Rukungiri district and there is a significant positive relationship between financial rewards and job performance.

I. GENERAL INTRODUCTION

A. Introduction

The study aimed at examining the relationship between rewards and job performance of teachers in private secondary schools in Rukungiri district, Uganda. This section entails the background of the study, statement of the problem, purpose, objectives, scope and conceptual framework.

a) Background of the study

In Uganda, issues regarding rewards and job performance are widely documented showing challenges facing the country's education sector. These relate to inputs by individuals, community and national outcomes such as student's academic performance, community wellbeing and national growth and development (Ministry of Education and Sports, 2003). Issues of poor rewards and poor job performance of teachers dodging are not addressed and their negative consequence could spill over to

various individual community and national outcomes (MOES, 2003). However, research about the effect of rewards on teachers' job performance in private schools in Uganda is still waiting to inform formulation of policies, for appropriate management of private schools in the country. The study of rewards and job performance of teachers in Rukungiri district was motivated by desire to fill this knowledge gap.

B. Statement of the problem

Rewards constitute one the important factors employers use to influence desirable employee job performance of an organization. Effective financial rewards include salaries, bonuses and allowances, non-financial rewards may be training and development, recognition and career advancement among others. Private schools in Rukungiri district offer a variety of financial and non-financial rewards as a way to motivate teachers' responsibilities.

Despite of the schools' efforts, the job performance of teachers in private secondary schoolsof Rukungiri district has been reported low and poor, characterized by wide spread and rampant absenteeism from school and late coming, dodging classes, lack of job commitment, poor teacher-student interaction, poor commitment and academic content among others (Rukungiri district Annual sector report, 2016). In view of such discrepancy, there is need to find out why the job performance of teachers is poor in spite of various rewards offered by their schools.

C. General objective

The general objective of this study was to establish the relationship between rewards and job performance of teachers in private secondary schools of Rukungiri district.

a) Specific objectives

To find out the relationship between financial rewards and job performance in private secondary schools of Rukungiri district.

To find out the relationship between non-financial rewards and job performance in private secondary schools of Rukungiri district.

D. Scope of the study

The study focused on rewards and job performance of teacher and private secondary schools in Rukungiri district. Rewards included financial rewards which were salaries, bonuses, allowances and non-financial rewards were training and development, recognition and career advancement and how these influence teachers' job performance. The study area considered was Rukungiri district. Among the selected private secondary schools

included; St. Raphael secondary school, Excel high school Buyanja, Holy field High school, Rwakiseta and Zed

foundation.

E. Conceptual frame work

Fig. 1: showing the conceptual framework on rewards and job performance

Source: Adopted from Nelson (2003) and Herm (2007) and modified by researcher (2022) to suit the study

The conceptual framework above show that rewards in terms of both financial and non-financial influence the job satisfaction of teachers in Rukungiri district. And that these

are influenced by Work, Co-worker and Supervision at the work place.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research design

The study employed a cross-sectional survey design. This involved collecting data over a period of two weeks from a sample of teachers, head teachers and bursars of selected private secondary schools in Rukungiri district. Questionnaire approach helped to describe the phenomenon as it appeared perpetuating into the relation and the effects.

random sample of subjects which is proportional to the size given in the stratum (Sekaran, 2003).

D. Data collection methods

The data collection methods employed included primary and secondary research methods of data collection. Primary data employed instruments such as questionnaire and key informants' interviews from where opinions collected were used to generate popular themes in the study. Secondary data employed instruments such as documentary reviews.

B. Study population

The current employ's list from Human resource departments of the private secondary schools availed the categories of teachers and other employees deemed in the study were scrutinized. The study targeted teachers in the five chosen private secondary schools in Rukungiri District 100 teachers and key informants (head teachers and school bursars) of the selected schools together making a total of 110 individuals.

E. Reliability and validity of instruments

Validity is the ability of an instrument to measure what it is supposed to measure (Amin 2005) and contended that a score of 0.7 and above is accepted. Validity of an instrument is done to ensure relevance, clarity, and simplicity of items in the questionnaires (Sekaran 2005). To ensure validity, the researcher reviewed interactive concerns regarding rewards and job performance and possible indicators of variables under investigation. Content validity index (CVI) for each item was determined using the formula;

C. Sample size determination and sampling procedure

The sample size of 86 respondents was determined based on Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table. The researcher sampled stratified random sampling in the selection of the 5 schools and purposive sampling on the head teachers and bursars. Stratified random sampling involved dividing the population into mutually exclusive strata, and selecting a

CVI = Total Number of items rated relevant by all respondents / Total number of items in the instrument and A CVI of 0.7 and above was considered satisfactory.

The reliability of instruments was arrived at through use of Cronbach Alpha test.

Variables	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha
Financial rewards	6	0.754
Non-financial rewards	8	0.802
Job performance	8	0.747

Table 1: reliability of analysis test

The table shows that the coefficients for the variables under investigation range from 0.747 to 0.802. According to Amin (2005) implies high inter-items consistency for each variable.

F. Data analysis

Data analysis involved closely related operations intended to summarize collected data and organize them in a manner that answers the research objectives, Amin (2005). The data was entered in Microsoft office Excel and later transferred to statistical package for social scientists (SPSS version 18.0) for analysis. Descriptive tables were used to express the percentages of the responses. And Pearson's

correlation coefficient was used to investigate the relationship between the study variables. In addition, the coefficient of determination was used to explain the strength of relationship between the study variables.

III. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS

A. Empirical findings from the study

a) Financial rewards and teachers job performance.

During the study 6 statements were presented to respondents who ranked them according to the level they agreed or disagreed with them.

Item on financial rewards(n=78)	SDA (%)	DA (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)
Salary paid compares well with my work effort at school	37	42	0	11	10
Salary paid compares well with that of my colleagues in this school	30	33	14	16	7
Salary paid compares well with that of teachers in other secondary schools	41	28	13	6	12
All teachers are often paid bonuses when they perform well	25	33	8	14	20
Allowances paid compares well with actual cost of transport and accommodation	37	28	5	17	13
Allowances paid compares with those of teachers in other secondary schools	27	27	20	12	14

Table 2: Respondents' perceptions on financial rewards and job performance

Source; primary data (2022)

Notes; SDA=strongly disagreed, DA=disagreed, N=neutral, A= agree, SA=strongly agreed

In order to assess the perceptions of teachers regarding the salary they were paid by their schools, the respondents were asked whether salary they were paid compares with their work effort at school. It emerged that 79% of respondents disagreed with the statement compared to 21% in agreement. In addition, study findings revealed 63% responses were in disagreement, with 14% not sure and 23% in agreement that salary they are paid compares well with that of their colleagues in their schools. Further, respondents were asked whether the salary they received compares well with that of teachers in other secondary schools. And study findings revealed that 69% were in disagreement compared to 18% only in agreement. The findings presented above mean that payment of salaries was perceived by teachers as being insufficient, discriminatory, uncompetitive and generally unfair. This leads to low commitment by encouraging absenteeism; teacher's discouraging qualified teachers to join their schools or themselves leaving these schools. Unfair perceived salaries lead to low teacher's involvement, by declining covering up absent colleagues with heavy loads, voluntary participation in school activities. Again, unfavorable salaries could lead to low teacher's morale, for example teachers 'enthusiasm and happiness for doing school related activities may drop drastically.

This is backed by statement from key respondents such as: *"we still have a challenge of paying our teachers' salaries which are at least compared to those elsewhere. Because of low salaries some of our teachers are less committed to their work and to the school in general. There is need for improving teachers' salaries to the level that matches salaries paid elsewhere, would improve job performance of teachers"*.

In order to assess the teachers' perceptions concerning the allowances they were paid by their schools; respondents were asked whether the allowances they were paid by their schools well compares with the actual cost of transport and accommodation. And the study findings revealed that majority 65% were in disagreement, 5% neutral and 30% in agreement. In responses to whether allowances they were paid well compare with those teachers in other secondary schools. Study findings revealed that majority 54% were in disagreement compared to only 26% agreement with 20% uncertain. The findings mean that allowances paid to most teachers in Rukungiri district are insufficient, uncompetitive and unfair. This could lead to low teacher commitment, absenteeism is rampant for example resulting into low teacher involvement, and low willingness to work beyond normal work hours and most probable, teachers' morale may be compromised because pride and enthusiasm in work place may be dented.

This is backed by statement from key respondents such as: *"Some of our teachers often miss their lessons because they come from very far, yet the school is unable to adequately meet their transport costs on a regular basis."*

While assessing teachers' perceptions about the bonuses they receive from their schools, respondents were asked whether all teachers are given bonuses when they perform well and the study findings revealed that 58% were in disagreement, with 8% uncertain and 34% in agreement. Such findings suggested that there was discrimination in awarding of bonuses to teachers and as such discrimination indicates unfair treatment of teachers which could affect morale, decreasing on enthusiasm and happiness among

teachers. Overall teachers had unfavorable perceptions about the financial rewards they receive from their schools.

The researcher having established the teachers ‘perceptions about the financial rewards in their schools in

response to job performance, he proceeded to investigate whether there is a statistical relationship between financial rewards and teachers ‘job performance and results are as below.

Variables		Financial rewards	Job performance
Financial rewards	Coefficient	1	0.784
	Sig.(2-tailed)		0.032
	N	78	78
Job Performance	Coefficient	0.784	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.032	
	N	78	78

Table 3: Correlation between financial rewards and teachers’ job performance

Source; primary data (2022)

Results revealed that there is a strong positive correlation between financial rewards and job performance of teachers as this was evidenced by the correlation coefficient of 0.784 that is statistically significant since p-value $0.032 < 0.05$. This implies that the favorable financial rewards are associated with high teachers’ performance, while unfavorable financial rewards are associated with poor teachers’ job performance.

b) Non-financial rewards and teacher’s job performance
The second research objective sought to find out the perception of teachers about non-financial rewards and their relation to the job performance of teachers in private secondary schools in Rukungiri district as the results are as in table 4 below.

Items on non-financial rewards (n=78)	SDA (%)	DA (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)
School usually recognizes teachers who perform outstandingly	24	16	0	32	28
Recognition I receive compares well with my outstanding performance	43	23	5	19	10
Equal recognition of teachers in the school who perform outstandingly	24	38	2	20	16
Way teachers are recognized in school compares with teachers in other schools	32	28	8	23	9
Schools conduct regular training and development programs for all teachers	25	14	9	34	18
There is equality in selection of teachers for training and development programs	37	27	2	18	16
Schools offer career advancement opportunities for all teacher	23	20	6	22	29
There is equality in access to career advancement opportunities for all teachers	42	21	7	15	15

Table 4: Respondents’ perceptions on the fairness of non-financial rewards in their school

Source; primary data (2022)

In order to comprehensively study on non-financial rewards and job performance, respondents were asked whether their schools usually recognize teachers who perform outstandingly. And the study findings revealed minority 40% respondents were in disagreement compared to majority 60% in agreement. However, when asked whether the recognition they usually receive compares well with their outstanding performance, most respondents (66%) disagreed with this item whereas 29% agreed. Generally, most respondents (62%) disagreed that there is equal recognition of teachers in the school who perform outstandingly compared to only 36% in agreement. Furthermore, results found out that 60% respondents disagreed when asked whether the way they were recognized compares with the practice elsewhere, while 32% agreed. Meaning recognition practices are unfavorable. This May lead to teacher morale, and pride and enthusiasm by teachers for doing work becoming low.

On training and development, teachers were asked whether their schools usually conduct regular training and development opportunities for them. Results revealed that 39% were in disagreement, 9% neutral, and majority 52% in agreement with the statement. Again, when asked whether all teachers had equal access to training and development opportunities offered by their schools, majority 64% respondents were in disagreement compared to 34% in agreement. Such finding suggests that the schools ‘training and development practices seemed unfair. Such unfair training and development practices may lead to low morale by teachers say teacher’s happiness to work in these schools and hope in their schools may become low. This may result to low teacher involvement and the quality of their work may also become low.

This is backed by statement from key respondents such as: “it is true not all teachers are given the chance to be trained because of the criteria followed in the selection process and such factors cannot be accessed by teachers themselves. But generally, he continued to say that performance of those who get such chances improves and that I think a school would consider giving opportunities to all teachers so as to enhance the general performance at their school”.

On the status of career advancement opportunities in their schools, teachers were asked whether schools usually carry out career advancement opportunities. It emerged that 43% of the respondents disagreed, 6% neutral and majority 22% agreed with the statement. It was found out that 63% of the respondents disagreed when asked whether they had equal access to career advancement opportunities provided by their schools while minority 30% agreed. This implies that access to career advancement opportunities by teacher

were unfair which may lead to teacher’s commitment and hence high teacher’s turnover. It can also result into low teacher morale, and the teachers hope in their school, happiness to work, and pride in work they do for their schools may be dented.

The overall picture concerning perceptions about the non-financial rewards offered by private secondary schools in Rukungiri district clearly indicated that most respondents disagreed with most items measuring behaviors of non-financial rewards. This implies that non-financial rewards were largely perceived unfair and unfavorable. This can negatively affect the performance of teachers in terms of commitment, involvement and morale.

The researcher further investigated whether there is a significant relationship between non-financial rewards and teachers’ job performance and results are as below.

Variables		Non-financial rewards	Job performance
Non-financial rewards	Coefficient	1	0.526
	Sig.(2-tailed)		0.018
	N	78	78
Job performance	Coefficient	0.526	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.018	
	N	78	78

Table 5: Correlation between non-financial rewards and teachers’ job performance

Source primary data (2022)

The results in the table 5 above showed a moderate positive relationship between non-financial rewards and job performance of teachers($r=0.526$) and this means that favorable non-financial rewards were associated with high teacher’s performance while unfavorable non-financial rewards were associated with poor teachers’ job performance.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusions from the study

Based on the study findings, the researcher concludes that financial rewards were poor and these were related to the current poor job performance of teachers in private secondary schools in Rukungiri district and there is a significant positive relationship between financial rewards and job performance.

Based on the study findings, the researcher concludes that the non-financial rewards were poor and these were related to the poor job performance of teachers in private secondary schools in Rukungiri district. Thus, if schools are to improve the job performance of teachers, they need to offer favorable non-financial rewards.

B. Recommendations

The study recommends that in order to enhance job performance of teachers in private secondary schools in Rukungiri district, there should be availability of financial resources through;

- Increases on teacher’s salaries to compare their work efforts and to compare well with salaries paid to their

colleagues and to other teachers in other schools in the contemporary.

- Pay allowances that mirror the actual costs of transport and accommodation in their areas and to compare those to their colleagues and to other teachers in other schools in the contemporary.
- Pay all teachers bonuses whenever they perform well in school so as to remove shock of discrimination among teachers.

The study recommends the following measures on non-financial rewards as a way to improving the job performance of teachers in private secondary schools in Rukungiri district.

- Offer teachers recognition that compares well with their outstanding performance, give all teachers who perform outstandingly equal recognition and adopt recognition practices in schools.
- offer all teachers equal opportunities to access training and development opportunities.
- give all qualifying teachers equal opportunities to access career advancement opportunities.

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REFERENCES

- [1.] Amin, M.E.2005, social science research: conception methodology and analysis. Makerere University Printery, Kampala
- [2.] Mugenda, O. M and Mugenda A.G (2003). Research Methods; *Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. ACTS Publishers, Nairobi Kenya
- [3.] Nelson, B (2003). Money is not the root of motivation. Health Care Registration.Vol. 2(10) PP7-9
- [4.] Rukungiri District Education Sector Performance report, 2016.
- [5.] Sekaran, U (2003). Research Methods for business (4thed.). Hoboken N.J Wiley and sons.